

NATIONAL AND CULTURAL SPECIFICS OF COMPLEX WORDS EXPRESSING A PERSON'S APPEARANCE AND CHARACTER IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7392019>

ELSEVIER

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Abstract: This article is devoted to the analysis of the national-cultural specificity of complex words expressing the appearance and character of a person in English and Uzbek languages. The main tasks of this work were the different approaches of linguists to the national-cultural problem, the interdependence of national-culture and language, and the activity of compound words in expressing this linguistic phenomenon.

Keywords: comparative linguistics, word composition, linguistic literature, lexical unit, compound words, Uzbek language, English language, lexicology, lexical-semantic groups, appearance and character of a person, national-cultural identity.

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Received: 01-12-2022

Accepted: 02-12-2022

Published: 22-12-2022

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Keywords: qiyosiy tilshunoslik, soʻz tarkibi, lingvistik adabiyot, leksik birlik, qoʻshma soʻzlar, oʻzbek tili, ingliz tili, leksikologiya, leksik-semantik guruhlar, shaxsning tashqi koʻrinishi va xarakteri, milliy-madaniy oʻziga xoslik.

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Abstract: Данная статья посвящена анализу национально-культурной специфики сложных слов, выражающих внешность и характер человека, в английском и узбекском языках. Основными задачами этой работы были разные подходы лингвистов к национально-культурной проблеме, взаимообусловленность национально-культуры и языка, активность сложных слов в выражении этого языкового явления.

Keywords: сравнительное языкознание, структура слова, лингвистическая литература, лексическая единица, сложные слова, узбекский язык, английский язык, лексикология, лексико-семантические группы, внешность и характер человека, национально-культурная идентичность

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INTRODUCTION

Word composition is one of the poorly developed linguistic phenomena in linguistics. The term word composition is interpreted by linguists in different ways and is understood extremely inconsistently and inaccurately.

Following I.V. Arnold, we understand the word structure as "a combination of two or, less often, three bases, functioning as one whole and standing out in the sentence as a special lexical unit due to its wholeness", "The word structure reflects the specifics of the language, since along with some common features for many languages, it has national, characteristic features for this language, making up one of the differences between one language from another".

Each language is linguistically unique relative to all other languages. On the one hand, it is also true that "this originality is a relative phenomenon: its content is determined by the language with which the given language is compared. What is specific in language A when compared with language B may be non-specific in comparison with language. On the other hand, a comparison of the system of unrelated languages, in particular, the English word composition with the Uzbek word system, contains catchier, large distinctive features of the English and Uzbek word composition.

Thus, it is possible to facilitate the task by comparing the phenomena of interest to us within unrelated languages. In this case, we will get a fairly informative description of the distinguishing features of English word composition from Uzbek. However, comparison within related, especially closely related, languages shows us a picture of distinctive details, subtleties, etc., since the main essential features in this case obviously coincide.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS

In the linguistic literature, there is not enough information about what is meant by the national specifics of composition. This issue is most fully covered in the book by E.A. Vasilevskaya "Composition in the Russian language", where there is a special chapter - "National originality of composition". The author of this book outlines the following parameters for describing the specifics of composition: 1) the presence or absence of composition as such in the language; 2) intensity, specific gravity, prevalence of compound words in the language; 3) types of compound words functioning in the language; 4) the correspondence of phrases in one language to compound words in another; 5) the ability to designate certain concepts with complex words or phrases; 6) the relationship of additions and fusions in the lexical and grammatical structure; 7) the presence or absence of a connecting vowel; 8) the location of the components, the order in which they follow one after another within the compound word. Even a cursory glance at this list suggests that some of the matching criteria are general in nature, that is, applicable to any or almost any matched pairs of languages, while other criteria are applicable only to certain pairs.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Of course, an important parameter is the inventory of models, the identification of which stems of which parts of speech can be combined with the

result in the form of a compound word. E. Sapir, in particular, speaks about this: "Some languages allow the composition of all or nearly all types of elements. Paiute, for instance, may compound noun with noun, adjective with noun, verb adverb with verb, verb with verb. Yana, an Indian language of California, can freely compound noun with noun and verb with noun, but not verb with verb. On the other hand Iroquois can compound only noun with verb, never noun and noun as in English or verb and verb as in so many other languages»

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

An interesting criterion is "the location of the components, the order in which they follow one after another within a compound word". Applying this criterion to identify the national specifics of composition, B. Ismailova compares words of the same meaning in a pair of languages and finds that in English compound words the arrangement of components is reversed compared to Kyrgyz, which emphasizes the difference between these languages in the field of composition. On the other hand, a commonality is found for the English and Kyrgyz languages. Of course, similarities or discrepancies in this regard can only be identified by comparing a large number of words vocabulary national language

This criterion is considered somewhat differently by E. Sapir, who writes: "... each language has its characteristic types of order of composition. In English the qualifying element regularly precedes: in certain other languages it follows. Sometimes both types are used in the same language, as in Yana, where "beef" is "liver-deer". The compounded object of verb precedes the verbal element in Paiute, Nahuatl, and Iroquois, follows it in Jana, Tsimshian, and Algonkin languages". As you can see, speaking about the order of elements in a compound word, E. Sapir does not compare words with the same meaning in two languages, but speaks about the arrangement of elements in the compound word "definition + defined" "object + action" or vice versa.

The national flavor of such nouns of the Uzbek language as *oqsaqol*, *olapes* is determined by national customs, beliefs, prejudices, and traditions. Among Uzbeks, a thick beard has always been considered a sign of nobility, and a man with a white beard received the name *oqsaqol* in the Uzbek language, which is not typical for the English language. This word is translated into English as a whole phrase, and man with white beard and mustache is an old man with a gray beard and mustache. Compound word, the appearance of which is associated with national prejudice: *olapes*. In countries with a subtropical and sharply continental climate, some people develop white spots on their skin. It was generally accepted that these people were "unclean hands". Thus, a complex noun appeared in the Uzbek language that characterizes a person, his appearance is *olapes*, the direct equivalent of which we will not find in English.

Nouns used to describe the appearance and character of a person are a word with one or more stems. Nouns used to describe a person's appearance may include simple nouns in English, and complex nouns in Uzbek: *blond - mallasoch - «блондин», «блондинка»; brunette - qorasoch - «брюнетка», «брюнет»*..

It should be noted that nouns with a simple stem used to describe a person's appearance create an image of a person as a whole, while nouns with a complex stem evaluate the appearance of the person being described, highlighting the conspicuous attribute of appearance. This phenomenon can be traced in both languages. For example, sunny-faced girl, well-built youth. Her steel-grey eyes go through you and see granite-hewn features (Christie, p. 157). His loosely-slung muscular arms were all ideal for the game (Doyle, p. 58).

In English: battleaxe - an unpleasant woman who tells people what to do in a determined and rather frightening way = VIRAGO (MAC, p. 110); lazybones - someone who is behaving in a lazy way = LAYABOUT: Come on, get out of bed, lazybones! (MAC, p. 852); cowboy - a man in stories and films called Westerns about the North American West. A cowboy's job was to look after CATTLE, but they are often shown in dangerous situations and especially having fights with NATIVE AMERICANS. A man whose job is to look after cows on a RANCH in the US (MAC, p. 342); chatterbox - someone who talks a lot (MAC, p. 242).

In the Uzbek language: oqsoqol "white-bearded, elder" - Bu oqsaqol ketsa, urniga yoshroq qorasoch keladi. (S. Siyoev. Yoruglik); humkalla "empty-headed". Ahmad brigadir humkalla o'gilchasiga kissasidan mayiz Olib Berdi. (S. Nurov. Maysalarni ayoq urmaydi); khushmuilov - "a man with a beautiful mustache." Yigitlar kulimsirab, o'rtadagi dumaloq yuzli, qushmuylov yigitga ishor qilishdi. (Kh. Sultonov. Onamning yurti); o'rtadagi so'rida o'tirgan baland bo'lyi qushmuilov yigit so'rini qasir-qusur qilib, o'zini pastga otdi. (S. Ahmad. Khukm). So, in the Uzbek language, the word mesh-qorin characterizes a person as a glutton. But in the semantic structure of the Uzbek word mesh-qorin there is also the sense "full person".

It should be noted that in the process of comparative and cross-cultural analysis, we found that compound words in the compared languages can be characterized by the presence of national cultural components. In Uzbek: kabobkhur "kebab lover, gourmet". *Bir kabobpaz boru, kabobkhurdan darak yuq* (I. Rakhim. Takdir); mayparast "drunkard". *Men sizing pulparast, molparasligingizga chidab keldim, ammo may-parast, maishatparasligingizga chidayolmay man.* (G'. Fulom. Toshkentliklar); bekorchihuzha "loafer". *Quruq qaytib borsang, anavi bekorchihuzhalardan qutilib bo'psan* (Yoshlik), mehmonnavoz (mehmondo'st) "hospitable". *Fe'li keng, so'zi bir bizning tog'liklar. Ko'p mehmonnavozdir bizning tog'liklar.* (X. Saloh. Tog - mening vatanim);

In English, we also find compound words with national and cultural components: chimney-head - having a round long head; goddess-like - like goddess or a god in some quality; blue-eyed boy - a young man who is admired because he is very successful, attractive etc. This word usually shows that you dislike people like this: Simmons, the blue-eyed boy of motor racing, has won again (MAC, p. 149); rabbit-toothed - a man with big front teeth like rabbit; beef-colored face - with a red face; beefcake - attractive men with large muscles, or pictures of men like this (MAC, p. 118); bullet-shaped head - having a small, round head. Hunchback - someone who has a large round part on their back that is caused by an unusual curve in their SPINE. You may see or hear this word but do not use it. Knucklehead - a stupid person = FOOL (MAC, p. 835); dogs body - someone who is forced to do all the jobs that no one else wants to do (MAC, p. 435); dunderhead - a stupid person = FOOL (MAC, p. 460).

The above compound words are nationally colored. These words name objects that are characteristic of the life, life, culture, social and historical development of the people and alien to some other people. Being carriers of national or historical color, they, as a rule, do not have exact matches in other languages.

The research material showed that this phenomenon can be traced in both languages. A deeper study of such phenomena is undoubtedly of great importance for expressing the national and cultural specificity of the languages under consideration. For example: *bald-head* - человек с лысой головой; *hunch-back* - *bukur odam* - горбун, *big-belly* - *meshqorin* - пузан, *white-skin* - *oqbadan* - человек с белой кожей, белый человек; *sarvqomat* - nice-looking - очень привлекательная, красивая женщина, *terakal* - *bald-pate* - человек с лысиной на макушке головы.

You can meet culturally determined epithets, which include a fictional image of culture (mythological heroes), for example: a John-Bull-like lady. The extravagant devil-may-care creature he portrayed on the stage (S. Maugham).

The analysis of the language material showed that lexico-semantic groups as color designations, names of flora and fauna play an important role in terms of the national and cultural specificity of compound words. In English: the Janitor was a horsey-looking customer (A. Coonin). She patted her mouse-colored hair with the pen (A. Coonin). There was a perplexed creature with a pear-shaped face (J.C. Gates). Kathleen had a small straight nose and large brown eyes. She was a plump, rosy-cheeked, wholesome apple-faced young woman (Ch. Dickens). Lister consented to listen and Mr. Ross blinked his cat-like-eyes and started (Th. Dreiser). He had egg-like head and frog-like jaws (Chesterton).

CONCLUSION

Thus, the study of the appearance and character of a person in terms of national and cultural specifics showed that compound words denoting the appearance and character of a person are nationally marked.

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